

Harmful Algae News

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The GLOBAL HAB Status Report (GHSR): 4 years later

Why a GHSR was planned

In issue 58 of HAN, we made a call to participate in the initiative to develop the first Global Harmful Algal Bloom Status Report (GHSR) to illustrate trends of HAB events by collecting all available data and published information at a global scale [1]. This exercise was motivated by a number of different reasons. Firstly, it was realised that after several decades of intensive research, the HAB field was dominated by the common perception of an increase of these phenomena around the world's seas. Yet so far no sound assessment of HAB patterns and trends had ever been attempted. That HABs were expanding and increasing has been commonly stated in the introductions of many scientific publications and research projects. Furthermore IPCC and GOOS reports used HAB increases as a flag to point to global change. Fluctuations and trends in the aquatic environment under the impact of human activities and hydrographic/climatic change can reasonably cause changes in abundance and distribution of algal species, either toxic or non-toxic. The underlying question is whether environmental and human-driven changes unequivocally determine a global increase of algal

blooms or their impacts. On the other hand, human activities can act as a multiplier for HAB detection because of intensification of observational activities driven by increased exploitation of the coastal zone, as well as progress in science, but the extent of these effects had never been quantified. Therefore, a data-based assessment was needed to disentangle the different issues leading to the current perception of HAB trends, and discern a possible spreading and intensification of bloom events driven by environmental and/or anthropogenic changes from the effects of a growing awareness resulting from improved knowledge and monitoring systems.

A second motivation for GHSR was the need to demonstrate the relevance of HAB data collection and systematization for scientific research and management activities. Data related to harmful algae events are regularly produced in relation to human health protection and seafood marketing issues, while detailed studies on toxic algae and algal bloom occurrence are published in a myriad of scientific papers not freely available. To collect these data in well organised and shared datasets allows us to perform robust statistical analy-

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Fig. 1. The Harmful Algae information system (HAIS) provides one user entry point for access to data and information on harmful algal species, their effects, their occurrences, the toxins, expertise on HABs, and key references.

Table 1. The three main databases concerning harmful microalgal species and their impacts. Toxic species cover all those known to include strains that produce toxins and are hence only potentially toxic. Asterisks indicate mandatory data and information (from [2]).

	Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Micro Algae	HABMAP-OBIS	HAEDAT
Field	Taxonomy and toxins	Biogeography	Socio-economics, health, ecology
Includes	List of toxic species	Toxic species records with or without impact	Non-toxic or toxic harmful events with an impact
Excludes	Non-toxic HAB species	Records of non-toxic HAB species	Records of blooms or toxic species or toxin concentrations in shellfish without impacts
Literature	References on species taxonomy* and toxicity*	References of species records*	References of the event or reports by national representatives entered when appropriate
Geographic coordinates	No	Yes*	Yes*
Time	No	Yes	Yes
Environmental data	No	At times in the literature cited	At times in the reports
Impacts	No	Not needed	Yes*
Source	Editors of the list	Regional groups of Editors	National representatives of IOC-ICES-PICES groups
Web site	www.marinespecies.org/hab/	ipt.iobis.org/hab	haedat.iode.org/

ses and meta-analyses aimed at tracing trends and variations of HABs at multiple spatial and temporal scales. Such analyses contribute to understanding the ecological and biological mechanisms underlying these phenomena, providing effective knowledge and forecasting tools in support of management and coastal space planning activities, to benefit the whole of society[2].

Thirdly, the GHSR was planned to give more visibility to a field of investigation that is important for both scientific and societal reasons in order to draw public attention and attract continued funding in support of HAB research. The case of the success of IPCC provides a remarkable example of how scientific knowledge can be disseminated outside academia, fuelling and supporting scientific research, influencing public opinion and decision-makers, and provoking societal change. In this respect HABs can be seen as the tip of the iceberg of complexity of the marine world, showing that invisible creatures that dominate it provide humankind with multiple benefits, but at times can pose health and economic risks to society. Capitalising on the knowledge gained through over 50 years of studies and monitoring of HABs to assess their

actual distribution and impacts is one of the ways to attract public attention.

How GHSR was produced

To address the GHSR aims a winning move was to involve the scientific community in a region by region collection, review and analysis of the relevant in-

formation made available by data input from national institutions, as well as the large HAB science community who had produced and published it in the literature. A main element of the operation was the support from the International Oceanographic Data Exchange programme IODE of IOC, which is in charge of the maintenance and development of the Harmful Algae Information System (HAIS, Fig. 1). The process was placed under the responsibility of an IOC Task Team under the Inter-governmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB). The first GHSR was produced with dedicated funding from the Government of Flanders (Belgium), which was used for meetings, training workshops and information technology development, and in-kind contribution from the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) in data compilation workshops, meetings and training.

GHSR planning and goals

GHSR consists of a number of intertwined initiatives and goals:

Improve and expand the databases on HABs. Among the HAB related databases, OBIS/HABMAP includes information on the distribution of potentially toxic species based on published literature while HAEDAT, collects data on harmful events produced by toxic or non toxic species that have an actual impact

Fig. 2. World map of the distribution of events associated with Paralytic Shellfish Toxins (red) combined with that of the occurrence of Alexandrium (blue). The HAIS mapping tool allows for any combination of species occurrence data (OBIS/HABMAP) and event data (HAEDAT).

on human health or activities, or on the environment (Table 1). Both databases rely on the volunteer contribution and inputs by regional editor groups and national representatives within ICES and IOC regional groups. Following our calls at the HAB conference in Brasil [3] and in HAN [1] as well as further contacts with HAB scientists from different areas of the world, the existing databases on HAB species distribution and HAB events were enriched with a considerable amount of new information. The whole activity led to an increase of more than double the number of HAEDAT records between March 2017 and December 2019 (from 4517 to 9503) and to increment the OBIS/HABMAP with data on HAB species distribution from several regions of the world. To coordinate this effort, workshops were organised during which databases and data input details were illustrated, to make data collection as easy and consistent as possible. Connected to this activity, a new user-interface was developed for HAIS (Harmful Algae information System, <https://data.hais.ioc-unesco.org>) with different options of data visualization combining OBIS records on the occurrence of toxic species with HAEDAT records on harmful algae events with impacts (Fig. 2).

Produce a collection of regional HAB overviews.

Lead HAB scientists from

Fig. 3. Microalgae of different taxonomic groups causing distinct HAB types. a) Paralytic Shellfish Toxin producing dinoflagellate *Alexandrium minutum*; b) Amnesic Shellfish Toxin producing diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata*; c) dinoflagellate *Ansanella granifera* causing discolorations off Cuba (from [5]); d) mucilage-producing diatom *Thalassiosira mala* associated with fish mortality (from [6]); e) Azaspiracid producing dinoflagellate *Azadinium dexteroporum*; f) picoplanktonic pelagophyte *Aureococcus anophagefferens* causing ecosystem disruptive blooms (from [7]); g) dinoflagellate *Akashiwo sanguinea* causing seawater discolorations; h) Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxin producing dinoflagellate *Dinophysis sacculus*; i) dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax fragilis* associated with mucilages damaging tourism and fisheries; j) prymnesiophyte *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* causing salmon mortalities in Norway [8].

different countries were invited to constitute groups of co-authors and conduct regional overviews based on the HAB databases described above as well as on literature overviews and expert judgement. An effort was made to cover

all regions of the world, although some areas had to be left out because of lack of information. An agreement was made with the Elsevier Journal *Harmful Algae* to host a special issue collecting the regional overviews.

From the work of 109 scientists from 35 countries, a variegated picture of HAB events and trends across the globe emerged, which reflects the diversity of the ca. 188 (toxic to humans and animals) to about 250 (including non-toxic) marine microorganisms that cause those events. Because of their multifaceted nature, harmful algal species may produce different kinds of adverse effects (Fig. 3) and respond in different ways to environmental drivers and their changes over time. Nonetheless the evidence was striking that HABs are posing a risk to human health and economics and affect human activities in all regions of the world [4].

Perform a meta-analysis of distribution trends of harmful event records.

In this effort, the expanded HAEDAT database was analysed, summing up the results in the first global scale analysis based on sound statistical analyses,

TEXTBOX 1. The main GHSR outcomes

- The GHSR has documented that **HABs are widespread** all over coastal waters of the world, wherever human activities and observations are in place, with impacts on human health, aquaculture, fisheries and tourism and overall environmental quality.
- An **extremely variegated picture of bloom types** has emerged at the regional and subregional scale, paralleled by that of the **causative species** which show different geographic and temporal ranges and ecological characteristics, as well as highly variable responses to environmental changes.
- Remarkable **differences in HAB socio-economic impacts** have also been revealed, mostly kept under control through ever improving monitoring activities, while the impacts on aquaculture, fisheries, use of natural marine resources and tourism continue to pose an economic risk in many regions.
- The intensity and frequency of HABs vary at a regional and local scale, with increasing or decreasing trends and sudden occasional outbursts but with **no uniform global trend that can be discerned from that of increased observational efforts**.
- The link between HABs and aquaculture has pointed to the relevance of observational activities and awareness to the perception of a global HAB increase, at the same time indicating that the **growing need to exploit marine resources and expand human activities in the coastal zone, driven by a growing human population will exacerbate HAB impacts in future years**.

Fig. 4. A. Numbers of HAB events recorded in twelve geographic regions. B. Relative abundance of different HAB types; and C. Seafood toxin syndromes. Paralytic Shellfish Toxins prevailed in East Coast America (ECA), South America (SAM), West Coast America (WCA), South East Asia (SEA) and North East Asia (NAS), Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins in the Mediterranean (MED) and Europe (EUR), and Ciguatera in the Indian Ocean (IND) and tropical Pacific (PAC). The Australia/New Zealand (ANZ) and Central America/Caribbean (CCA) regions displayed mixtures of events, while Benguela (BENG) had a large proportion of other syndromes (from [9]).

Fig. 5. Relationship between changes in aquaculture production and HAB events recorded in HAEDAT in the period 1985-2018. A. Changes in five regions of tonnage of Aquaculture Production of fish, molluscs, crustaceans and aquatic plants; see the legend of Fig. 4 for abbreviations; and B. Meta-analysis of HAEDAT events over time vs. Aquaculture. Weighted mean correlations (filled circles) are shown with 99% confidence limits (bars). The overall number of HAEDAT events over time was significantly correlated with aquaculture production (bottom), as seen from the confidence bar limit above the 0 value line (from [9]).

using the whole OBIS phytoplankton dataset as a proxy for observational effort changes over the years. In addition, a FAO dataset on aquaculture in different regions was used to take into account the trends in activities that imply an increase of monitoring operations. Trends were calculated at the regional and global scale. The main conclusion was the lack of any uniform global trend in the number of harmful algal events and their distribution over time, once data were adjusted for regional variations in observational activities. Trends were instead variable and contrasting among different regions, where they were characterised by different types of events, harmful species and emerging impacts (Fig. 4). A clear relationship was found however between the trends of harmful algal events and the monitoring effort associated with the development of aquaculture operations in coastal areas (Fig. 5), leading to the conclusion that the latter is at the base of the perceived increase in harmful algae events, while there is no empirical support for broad statements regarding increasing global trends [9].

GHSR outreach to the broader community

It has been imperative not only to communicate the main results of our work (see textbox 1) within our HAB Science discipline (i.e. the *Harmful Algae* special issue) but to reach the climate, environmental, fisheries, health disciplines as well as broader society and politicians. Therefore a 'Scientific summary for policy makers' was prepared aimed at sharing the GHSR results but also to explain the complexity of the HAB phenomena to a larger community [10]. Basically using the material from the scientific publications, the summary was written in plain language, supplied with colour images, and published on the web at <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000378691>.

To further share the GHSR results, at the end of the whole project, with the release of the various publications and the new arrangement of the OBIS/HAIS website, a series of initiatives were taken to disseminate and promote the results obtained to the media and the scientific community. Interviews with the main GHSR Authors were arranged with press agents from all over the wor-

Fig. 6. The launch of the GHSR was well covered in the global press; here some examples from different continents.

ld, resulting in numerous newspaper articles as well as web news (Fig. 6). An open webinar was organised inviting the Editors and the lead Authors of the Special Issue papers, along with the OBIS contributors to HAIS development, to communicate to the rest of the scientific communities the condensed results of the regional overviews and of the GHSR as a whole. In addition, more extended presentations of each of the regional overviews were prepared in the form of videos which are currently available on YouTube (Textbox 2).

The Nature Communications Earth & Environment synthesis publication [9] was downloaded 6400 times in its first 2 months, 110 on-line stories and 6 newspaper stories were published, 5 TV and radio programs delivered, which reached 27 countries, and were communicated in 8 languages. Finally, two GHSR presentations are planned at the 19th International Conference on Harmful Algae, Mexico, 10-15 October 2021.

GHSR problems and limitations

The GHSR identified a number of limitations in the current formats of the databases, HAEDAT and OBIS/HABMAP, which are far from complete. Whole regions such as the Indian Ocean, Africa, eastern south Atlantic coasts and southern-eastern Mediterranean coasts are

largely unexplored. Even in well studied parts of the world, no data are available for large coastal strips.

The way the data were historically collected make them sometimes difficult to handle quantitatively [2]. For example, the number of harmful algal

events recorded in HAEDAT may not correspond to actual HAB trends in a given region, but vary in relation to changing seafood marketing or HAB monitoring methodologies. Similarly, the higher number of potentially toxic species in selected regions and lack of species in others may simply reflect taxonomic expertise at the local scale.

While the GHSR synthesis attempted to address questions of global increase of frequency and distribution of HABs, data on the **intensity of HABs** as well as the **magnitude of their societal impacts** were not widely available. Using the number of HAB events blurs the actual impacts they may have exerted, because of the lack of quantitative data on the associated economic or well-being losses. An aquaculture ban (toxins in seafood), the closure of a beach (toxic aerosol), a human victim of seafood poisoning, a water discoloration perceived by the public or impairing tourism, currently all count in the same way in the present settings of the HAEDAT databases.

While some regional studies touched upon trends in toxins or in harmful species, neither regional nor global statistical analyses systematically took into account quantitative data of potentially toxic species abundances, and their link to ecological/climate conditions.

TEXTBOX 2.
Regional overview presentations

GHSR Synthesis
<https://youtu.be/Xn5kGJxeiHs>

Canada
https://youtu.be/_UbTWeV9wtY

Ciguatera
<https://youtu.be/kvDxVFVHEf0>

Australia and New Zealand
<https://youtu.be/QRRTED76E7g>

East Asia
<https://youtu.be/DCsEXtyX8bs>

The Philippines and Malaysia
<https://youtu.be/vi-fHGk0Qnc>

US
<https://youtu.be/uvDMQUtIICk>

North Atlantic Margin
<https://youtu.be/Hmois4MOI6o>

Northern Europe
<https://youtu.be/tV7SxVDs43g>

Mediterranean
<https://youtu.be/VJh-cg-N8Y>

Future perspectives

The GHSR was initially planned to be the first of a series of periodic global overviews along the line of IPCC climate reports. However, the results obtained so far demonstrate that, while impacts from HABs are expected to increase driven by the growth of the human population and increasing exploitation of marine resources, the question whether HABs are increasing globally is inappropriate. Considering the heterogeneity of the phenomena and their differing importance from place to place, the issues of HAB status and trends should be addressed at the regional and subregional scale with a focus on individual HAB types and species involved and using a fully multidisciplinary approach. Therefore, having this first phase of GHSR pursuing a global assessment come to an end, a new series of goals and initiatives need to be planned for future years.

At the global scale, the need remains to keep on collecting data and analyse them in a coordinated way, promoting the development of existing and new organised databases and analytical tools and supporting comparative ecological research on individual species and case-studies, thus scaling up the results of local research to a wider scale. The involvement of climate modellers and establishment of nutrient data bases (e.g., in relation to expanding aquaculture) is also needed.

The IPHAB Task Team on HAIS and GHSR will continue its activities, acting as an editorial advisory group for HAIS/GHSR and advise on requirements for HAIS adjustments, quality control and web site edits as well as advise and encourage regional groups and editors on HAB data compilation and their submission to OBIS/HABMAP and HAEDAT. The great spatial heterogeneity highlighted by the GHSR and lack of information for whole areas will be addressed by the IPHAB Task Team by engaging focal points in those regions to build up data for better geographical coverage.

The Task Team is also responsible to engage with working groups, groups of experts and individual scientists to identify time series of phytoplankton data including information on HAB species. There is potential for collaborations with the IOC-SCOR Global-HAB science programme and the IOC

Working Group to Investigate Climate Change and Global Trends of Phytoplankton in the Oceans (TrendsPO, Chair Peter.A.Thompson@csiro.au) to assist with a quantitative approach to investigate the relationships between environmental conditions and blooms of individual harmful algal species and their impacts.

Future development work for HAIS as a data system and thus future editions of the GHSR will depend on new sponsorships. While countries or institutions may be willing to support regional trend analysis and data collection it is a central challenge not to lose track of the bigger global aims that play at the level of IPCC (climate) and FAO (aquaculture). A coordination effort is needed to join up regional activities into a global approach.

The ideal would be to attract IPCC type funding that could support a sustained process leading to the regular GHSR delivery. This could include the establishment of a centralised service to coordinate and facilitate data entry for HAEDAT and OBIS, and act as a facility for data analysis workshops and training. One option would be to develop the GHSR as a UN Decade activity as a component of several larger programmes already submitted for endorsement to the Decade Secretariat. There could also be a potential for HAIS/GHSR to be a separate Decade activity, if philanthropic organisations are to be approached for funding. These options will be pursued in more detail by the IPHAB Task Team chaired by Eileen.Bresnan@gov.scot.

To put our ultimate GHSR aims in perspective, it emerges that, beyond considerable progress in management and several reasonable hypotheses, no clear explanations are still available for the prevalence of certain HAB types in some areas and their absence in others, nor for the locally decreasing or increasing trends and range expansions of some species, while questions on the outcomes of the ongoing environmental and anthropogenic changes remain mostly unanswered. There is thus a direct link that needs to be reinforced between our scientific understanding of HAB species population dynamic in a changing environment and our ability to analyse and understand trends for species occurrence patterns and HAB events.

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Fish filler *Heterosigma akashiwo* in Comau Fjord, Southern Chile

In early spring of 1988, a massive bloom of the alga *Heterosigma akashiwo* was observed in Comau Fjord (42°22'10"S), Los Lagos, southern Chile, resulting in severe impacts to the local salmon in-

dustry [1]. Over three decades later, on March 16th, 2021, approximately 400 cell/mL of *H. akashiwo* were detected, with a particularly noticeable surface distribution at the head of Comau Fjord

(Fig. 1). Ten days later, concentrations increased to 35000 cell/mL, forming intense brown patches in the water and a rise in HAB_f INDEX to 333 units, resulting in significant impact to local salmon farms [2]. During Easter celebrations on April 1st 2021 notable brown patches were seen extending approximately two thirds of the length of the fjord and at both margins. Most of the cell aggregation was contained within the Comau Fjord, although some patches were also observed in areas near the mouth of the fjord (Fig. 1).

The Oceanographic and Environmental Program of Salmonids (POAS) made it possible to clearly define the spatio-temporal origin of the bloom at the head of the fjord just prior to March 16th, 2021. Analysis of fish behavior, meteorological conditions, microscopic/FlowCam imaging and fluorescent photosynthesis analysis all indicated the bloom was over by April 4th, 2021. However, on April 16th, 2021 a second peak occurred, further damaging local fish farms (Figs. 2-3). Cells in the second peak of the bloom were healthy, highly mobile and had very high photosynthetic efficiency (Fv/Fm) based on FRRf3 [3]. Induction curves of active fluorescence of PSII show clear differences between the mouth and head of the fjord, and also in the water column due to species composition of phytoplankton and their respective abundances.

The phytoplankton composition and abundance within the Comau Fjord showed a mono-specific assemblage with more than 93 % comprised of *H. akashiwo* cells (Fig. 3). Few diatom species were observed and only outside the fjord, i.e., a typical ecological attribute of this biological event [4, 5].

Final remarks

The *H. akashiwo* bloom originated at the head of Comau fjord on March 16th, 2021 with cells that were poorly shaped, fragile, inactive and with low rates of photosynthesis, albeit at high concentrations (400 cells/mL, with a HAB_f INDEX = 111). Within two weeks cells recovered, restoring morpho-physiological signals (Fig. 3) and remained in the fjord for 40 days until April 25th, 2021. The very high concentrations of *H. akashiwo* and brown patches set a record of the HAB_f INDEX = 668, even higher than those

Fig. 1. Top: Map showing location of Comau Fjord in Los Lagos province, Chile. Middle: Patches of *Heterosigma akashiwo* in Comau Fjord, where maximal cell concentrations were found at the head of the fjord (red spot in the map). Bottom: A salmon farm in Magallanes province, Chilean Patagonia.

Fig. 2. Temporal distribution of the HAB_f INDEX in Comau Fjord during the bloom

observed in the 2016 *Pseudochattonella* bloom due to the high concentrations of raphidophyte cells.

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Fig. 3. Microscopy image of a sample from Comau Fjord, March 28th, 2021 showing a mono-specific bloom of *H. akashiwo*

Harmful Algae News (HAN) DOI Available

In order that all contributors and the whole HAB community can cite the HAN articles to mutual benefit, we have assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to each issue published between 2012 and 2021. **Issues PUBLISHED before 2012 will be dealt with before the end of this year.** For the upcoming new issues, the DOI will be printed on the newslet-

ter front cover. The articles can be cited in the following format, which will vary according to the particular requests from each journal:

Author's Name Year. Article title. In Editors' names (Eds.). *HAN*. Location of the article. Publisher. DOI

For example:

Kazumi Wakita.2021. *SHIOHIGARI* and

PSP toxins in Japan: Initiatives to save traditional recreational clam picking. In Reguera B & E Bresnan (Eds) *HAN* 67, UNESCO, pp 1-3 doi: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109703>

The list of links will also be found in the new IOC HAB website **to be launched in November.**

Harmful Algae News 67:
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109703>
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Harmful Algae News 64:
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Harmful Algae News 63:
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Harmful Algae News 62:
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Harmful Algae News 47:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5159137>
Harmful Algae News 46:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5159171>
Harmful Algae News 45:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5159201>

First report of a *Fibrocapsa japonica* Toriumi & Tanako bloom in the northern Humboldt current ecosystem

Fig. 1. Sampling sites in Miraflores Bay, Callao (12°S) and Paracas Bay, Pisco (13.70°S). February – March 2020

Raphidophycean flagellates associated with massive fish kills have been reported worldwide. High density blooms of species from this class cause physical obstruction to fish gills and mucus excretion, and are associated with production of hemolytic substances, such as polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) and reactive oxygen species (ROS) [1].

Among the most representative Raphidophycean species, *Olisthodiscus luteus* and *Heterosigma akashiwo* have been recorded in Peru forming extensive Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) between spring and autumn [2-5], although their potential effects in the ecosystem have not been elucidated. *Fibrocapsa japonica* is widely distributed in temperate and tropical seas. In South America, there are records of this species from Brazil and Uruguay [6-7]. This is the first report of *Fibrocapsa japonica* blooms in two upwelling areas: off Callao (Miraflores Bay 12°S) and Pisco (Paracas Bay 13.70°S in the coastal waters of Central and Southern Perú (Fig. 1). This HAB event occurred during the austral summer, between February 25 and March 11 2020. Yellowish-brown patches, extending 60nm from the coast (off Callao) were observed. In Pisco, patches were observed just inside the bay.

Surface water samples were col-

lected from seven stations for analysis of phytoplankton and measurement of hydrobiological parameters (Fig. 1). Microscopic examination and micrographs were made with a NIKON ECLIPSE TiU inverted microscope using a Nikon Digital Sight DS-U3 camera and Nis el-

Fig. 2. a) *Fibrocapsa japonica* living cell, the mucocysts, trichocysts and the flagella are observed in the sub-apical part of the cell. b) *F. japonica* in cell lysis a few seconds after its death (without preservation) expelling the trichocysts.

lected from seven stations for analysis of phytoplankton and measurement of hydrobiological parameters (Fig. 1). Microscopic examination and micrographs were made with a NIKON ECLIPSE TiU inverted microscope using a Nikon Digital Sight DS-U3 camera and Nis element D software. Differential Interference Contrast (DIC-Nomarski) was used to capture details of living cells. Cell counts were carried out using 1 mL Sedgwick Rafter chambers. The specimens from Perú were characterized by slightly dorso-ventrally compressed oval shaped cells with the presence of groups of large trichocysts or mucocysts, located in the posterior end (Fig. 2a). The cell size was approximately 24 µm long and 16.73 µm wide. In general, morphological characteristics observed agreed with those from previous description of the species [8-9].

Fixed samples were not suitable for a clear observation of the cells, because fixatives commonly used in monitoring projects caused disintegration of the cells, with irregular filaments attached to the raspberry-like specimen produced after the ejection of the trichocysts (Fig. 2b).

This *F. japonica* event was related to unusual environmental conditions that promoted bloom development (Fig. 3). In Callao, the bloom was associated with sea surface temperature (SST) values ranging from 23.5 to 25.6 °C, salinity 35.01 to 35.26 PSU, dissolved oxygen between 5.90 and 12 mL L⁻¹, with an average saturation of 166.45%. Mean cell concentration was 38 x 10⁵ cells L⁻¹. And the cell maximum (87 x 10⁵ cells L⁻¹) was recorded at station A (oxygen level 12 mL L⁻¹). In Pisco, environmental conditions were influenced by a frequent event in summer, the outflow of continental waters into the coastal zone (Fig. 4) [4]. SST values were 23.4 - 26.1 °C, salinity 33.829 - 34.102 PSU, and oxygen 6.04 - 7.90 mL L⁻¹ with an average saturation of 146.90%. Mean cell concentration of *F. japonica* was 8.41 x 10⁵ cells. L⁻¹. A cell maximum of 18 x 10⁵ cells L⁻¹ was found at station D off El Chaco, associated with dissolved oxygen of 6.04 mL L⁻¹.

No mortalities of fish or any other marine organisms were reported associated with the *F. japonica* blooms in the two above mentioned areas but there was abundant production of foam.

According to [10], the wide temperature range tolerated by this species (4 to 32 °C), with an optimal growth rate associated with a salinity of 26 PSU [1] classifies *F. japonica* as a eurythermal and eurohaline species, a fact which would explain its wide distribution.

Fig. 3. T-S Diagram for cell concentrations ($\text{cell} \cdot 10^5 \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) of *F. japonica* in Callao (12°S), Pisco (13.70°S)

This species thrives on eutrophic environments and is frequently observed in coastal and brackish waters [11]. These conditions agree with those observed in Miraflores and Paracas bays on the Peruvian coast.

This is the first report of *Fibrocapsa japonica* in these latitudes. Blooms of this species in Perú may pose a potential risk for the fisheries and aquaculture sectors. Further research is needed to unveil the harmful or toxic effects produced by this Raphidophycean species in the ecosystem.

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Fig. 4. Surface distribution of temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), salinity (psu) and oxygen (mL L^{-1}) in Paracas Bay, Pisco (February 2020).

First major bloom of *Trichodesmium erythraeum* (Cyanophyceae) and *Prorocentrum rhathymum* (Dinophyceae) in Yelapa Jalisco, México

Fig. 1. Sampling station in Yelapa Jalisco, Bahía de Banderas, Mexican Pacific coast, during the September 2019 bloom of *Trichodesmium erythraeum* and *Prorocentrum rhathymum*

This report of a harmful algal bloom (HAB) event from Yelapa Jalisco in Bahía de Banderas, México (Fig.1) describes for the first time a bloom of *Trichodesmium erythraeum* tufts co-occurring with high densities of the benthic dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum rhathymum* in

phytoplankton samples during September 2019.

The microalgae checklist from a regional monitoring programme 2000 – 2001 consisted of five categories: i) high biomass bloom forming species; ii) toxin producing species harmful to hu-

man health; iii) species which can cause skin problems through direct contact; iv) species which are toxic to other marine organisms (especially ichthyotoxic), and v) species that do not cause any problems *in situ* but have been found to produce toxins in culture [1, 4].

Blooms of *T. erythraeum* and *P. rhathymum* have not previously been recorded in the historic phytoplankton data from this region, even though both species are included in the list of microalgae that form HAB events in the coastal waters of the Gulf of California and in the Mexican Pacific [3]. The phytoplankton sample consisted almost entirely of tufts (parallel arrays, filaments) of *T. erythraeum* and oval cells of *P. rhathymum* (Fig. 2) as co-dominant species with densities of 1658×10^6 and 78×10^3 cells l^{-1} respectively. Some local fishermen reported dead fish, possibly caused by the anoxic conditions that may arise from decaying marine blooms [4], however due to equipment limitations, cyanotoxins and other phycotoxins were not analyzed. In addition, the presence of these microalgae reveals a potential risk of DSP contamination and hemolytic toxins from *P. rhathymum* [4], and a latent threat of neurotoxins, hepatotoxins, ciguatoxins, microcystin analogues, cylindrospermopsin and saxitoxin from the presence of *T. erythraeum* [2, 3].

The occurrence of these species has increased the algae checklist and current geographical expansion in Banderas Bay, where the factors that could favor these blooms are mostly related to coastal nutrient enrichment, mainly due to seasonal rains and high river discharge. On the other hand, the high abundance of the epibenthic *P. rhathymum* in surface waters could be associated with floating debris due to the seasonal increase of *Sargassum* and other macroalgal drift. This floating debris provides adequate substrate and an important vector for the dispersal of potentially toxic and benthic species of dinoflagellates. Satellite chlorophyll-*a* concentration from NOAA data sets were relatively low ($< 3 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$) (Fig. 3A). Typically temperature values range from 32.58 to 24.3 °C (Fig. 3B) and salinity from 0.43 to 36.59 psu for this period of the year due to the influence of tropical water [5].

Fig. 2. Light microscope (LM) micrographs of phytoplankton samples: a-c *Trichodesmium erythraeum*, d-e *Prorocentrum rhathymum* from Yelapa Jalisco, México

Fig. 3. Top: Temporal distribution of Chlorophyll a concentration (mg m^{-3}) in the study area during September-2019. Bottom: Mean sea surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) in Yelapa Jalisco México

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Training HAIS-HAEDAT to ANCA-IOCARIBE

The regional IOC HAB group ANCA-IOCARIBE is preparing training on the use of and data upload to the Harmful Algal Information System and its Harmful Algal Event Database (HAIS-HAEDAT) at the end of November 2021. This course aims to strengthen the registration of HAB events in the Caribbean region. The information available in HAIS is expected to be used for mechanistic models of biological and ecological processes associated with HAB events.

An example of this type of model is the IRMA, Aerobic Anoxic Mortality Risk Index, developed as a re-

sult of massive fish kills in the Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta - Colombian Caribbean [1-2], which occur recurrently, not only there, but also in many other coastal systems of the Caribbean. Implementing IRMA will serve as an early warning tool, an important input for a risk management system.

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Unexpected *Prorocentrum* bloom and associated gelatinous zooplankton in Alexandria, Egypt

We investigated an unprecedented, massive bloom of the dinoflagellate species *Prorocentrum minimum* and *P. triestinum* which co-occurred with dense swarms of the salp *Thalia democratica*. To our knowledge this bloom, considered an exceptional spring bloom in Alexandria waters, has never been reported anywhere else in the world. Blooms of *P. minimum* and *P. triestinum* during spring and summer have been recorded as a fairly regular feature of the annual phytoplankton succession in Alexandria waters [1-3].

The small salp, *Thalia democratica*, by virtue of its rapid asexual reproduction [4] is able to form extensive swarms [5] yet the physiological and oceanographic factors influencing the magnitude of these swarms are poorly understood [6-8]. The species is a common component of the zooplankton population in Egyptian waters, but not abundant [9]. Information about co-occurring blooms of pelagic tunicate and dinoflagellate species is still poor. We believe these dinoflagellate and gelatinous zooplankton species behave as opportunistic groups.

During routine weekly sampling for the project "Assessment of red tide phe-

nomena in the Egyptian neritic waters: causes and impacts", a visible reddish water discoloration extending approximately 10 Km was suddenly observed near the Alexandria coast between 4-6 May, 2021. The water discoloration at a semi-enclosed station (about 400m long) on 5 May was very unique. The basin was distinctly divided into two separate parts where two water masses of different water discoloration were seen; a reddish area at the Eastern part where dinoflagellates were significantly abundant, and dense white layers of *T. democratica* swarms at the west (Fig. 1). The whole area is part of an ongoing initiative for the protection of Alexandria coastal areas where thousands of cement blocks and tons of rocks are dispersed into the sea, creating semi-closed small basins. These small basins act as traps to extend the duration of the bloom. No fish and/or invertebrate mortality was detected, but the bloom appeared to be harmful for macroalgae as hundreds of individuals of the phaeophyte *Colpomenia sinuosa* were found dead on the beach.

The physicochemical conditions during the peak of the bloom included low temperature (23.8 °C), relatively

high salinity (37.075), intensely stratified water column, high pH (8.65), and very high nitrate levels (8.98 μM), while phosphate levels were severely reduced (0.55 μM). The bloom was composed of *P. minimum* (2.2×10^6 cells L^{-1} , contributing to 98.21% of the total standing crop) and *P. triestinum* (0.04×10^6 cells L^{-1}). Chlorophyll *a* levels during the bloom were 19.17 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, DO_2 , 10.69 mg L^{-1} , 160.81, and OM 5.6 $\text{mg O}_2 \text{ l}^{-1}$. The bloom was of a very short duration, with partial dissipation recorded on 6 May with scattered aggregations near the coast driven by changes in wind speed and direction.

Grazing by *T. democratica*, which is known to exhibit efficient feeding strategies [6], capable of depleting phytoplankton production and feeding actively on autotrophic dinoflagellates [10,11], may be the reason behind the rapid dissipation of the dinoflagellate bloom. Blooms of the toxigenic *P. minimum* may constitute a good food source for salps [12].

Why the intense masses of *T. democratica* occurred at a certain stations is unclear. The proliferation of *T. democratica* were associated with the relatively lower temperature, salinity and adequate food supply in agreement with previous findings [13]. The disappearance of the white-coloured swarms of *T. democratica* can be probably attributed to wind dispersal and increased temperature. Similar to other studies [8] our results were unsuccessful in relating abundances of *T. democratica* to physical conditions. Among other suggested causes is the salp clogging due to the high concentration of organic materials and phytoplankton production. Salps themselves serve as prey for numerous fish species [14]. These factors should be further verified. Our results agree with other studies concluding that blooms of *T. democratica* may appear suddenly over different spatial scales, last for a short time and suddenly disappear with no specific environmental drivers defined [15].

These blooms might be blamed on anthropogenic stressors, such as eutrophication, and modification of habitats. It is expected that the paradigm of gelatinous zooplankton blooms will increase in the future with cascading

Fig. 1. Photo of the dense white discoloration due to *Thalia democratica* swarms

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Elucidating the origin of tetrodotoxin in New Zealand bivalves

Tetrodotoxin (TTX) is a potent neurotoxin that acts by selectively targeting sodium channels, blocking propagation of action potentials and causing paralysis [1]. It has been responsible for countless human intoxications and deaths around the world, particularly in Japan, from consumption of pufferfish. The distribution of TTX and its analogues is remarkably diverse, and the toxin has been detected in organisms from marine, freshwater and terrestrial environments [2]. Increasing detections of TTX in aquaculture species not typically associated with TTX, such as edible bivalves and gastropods, has drawn considerable attention to the toxin, reinvigorating scientific interest and regulatory concerns. We found reports of TTX in 18 species of edible shellfish species from ten countries since the 1980's, with some reports above the safe threshold established by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) of 44 µg of TTX per kg of shellfish [3].

Despite decades of research, the exact origin of TTX remains a mystery. Current literature supports three hypotheses: endogenous production, symbiotic bacteria (including cyanobacteria), or direct bioaccumulation through a dietary source. In 2009, the sea slug *Pleurobranchaea maculata* was found to contain high concentrations of TTX in New Zealand [4] and an extensive research programme to explore the origin of TTX in *P. maculata* in New Zealand was launched. During this research, *Paphies australis*, an endemic clam, was found to accumulate high concentrations of TTX (800 µg kg⁻¹) [5]. A Ph.D. study was undertaken to elucidate the source of TTX in these clams that are a common food source and are culturally important in New Zealand. *Paphies australis* are largely sessile and found in subtidal habitats, making them highly amendable organisms to investigate the source of TTX.

In this Ph.D. study, a multiple line of evidence approach was used to investigate potential TTX producers. This included histological and analytical techniques to explore the micro-distribution of TTX within the organs of

P. australis, aquaria studies to investigate the depuration and uptake of TTX, field studies to explore the variations in TTX concentrations from different *P. australis* populations and other bivalve species in New Zealand, and molecular analyses. Immunohistological analysis of *P. australis* tissues employing a TTX monoclonal antibody demonstrated that TTX was present in the outer cells of the siphons, and also in the digestive system, foot and gill tissues [6]. These results were supported by chemical analysis using LC-MS/MS. Observing TTX in organs involved in feeding provided initial evidence to support the hypotheses of an exogenous source in *P. australis* and presence in siphon tips shows that TTX could be used as a chemical defence against predators.

The TTX depuration rate in *P. australis* was then assessed by maintaining TTX-bearing individuals in captivity and feeding them a non-toxic diet for 150 days. The bivalves significantly depurated the toxin (0.4% of total toxin content per day) and there was a rapid decline of the toxin in their digestive glands with only traces amounts remaining after 21 days [7]. This result provides evidence to support the hy-

pothesis that *P. australis* do not endogenously produce TTX.

During field surveys, *P. australis* from 10 different sites around New Zealand were harvested and tested for TTX. There were significant differences in TTX concentrations from the different sites. All *P. australis* contained TTX but bivalves from the warmer North Island sites contained significantly higher concentrations than those from the South Island. These results provided further evidence to support the proposition that the source of TTX in *P. australis* is likely exogenous, varying in abundance by location [7]. I hypothesised that the source is a warm-water-adapted TTX producer that is mostly present or more prevalent in warmer climates, or that TTX production is triggered by warmer temperatures.

To explore this possibility further, metabarcoding was used to investigate the bacteria, including cyanobacteria, present in the digestive glands and siphons of *P. australis* from the 10 sites with different TTX concentrations and collected monthly over a year from one site with high TTX concentrations. Marine cyanobacteria, in particular picocyanobacteria (e.g., *Cyanobium*, *Synechococcus*, *Pleurocapsa*, and *Prochlorococcus*), were found in all samples collected from sites containing the highest amount of TTX and were present in the core microbiome of TTX-bearing *P.*

Fig. 1. Diagram synthesising the main hypotheses regarding the accumulation of tetrodotoxin in the different organs of the New Zealand clam *Paphies australis* (Created with BioRender.com)

australis [8]. Cyanobacteria are well known for producing a wide range of marine and freshwater toxins and this finding warrants further investigation.

Lastly, the possibility that wild *P. australis* could sequester and accumulate TTX from a dietary source was assessed. A novel method to artificially feed a controlled amount of TTX to bivalves was developed. The micro-encapsulation method incorporated humic acid so that the water-soluble TTX was bound to a solid substance. The main finding from this study was that *P. australis* can rapidly accumulate TTX from an external dietary source and concentrations were much higher (> 100 µg kg⁻¹) than the safe threshold in bivalves established by the EFSA (44 µg kg⁻¹) in under two weeks [9]. This further strengthens the hypothesis that bivalves most likely accumulate TTX from their diet.

Based on the key results from my Ph.D. thesis and in concert with previ-

ous studies on the subject, I hypothesize that *P. australis* are obtaining TTX from a dietary source and there are three main possible routes of accumulation which are summarised in Figure 1. My thesis has addressed several critical knowledge gaps in our understanding of the source of TTX in bivalves worldwide and I am open for future collaborations to solve this mystery.

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Continued from page 13

socio-economic consequences for fisheries and tourism.

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A European Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) network

Fig. 1 Map showing locations of IFCBs operated in Europe until June 2021 and institutes operating the systems. Not all systems are fully operational. NIVA plans to operate one IFCB as part of ferrybox system on route Oslo-Kiel and SMHI plans to operate an IFCB during cruises with R/V Svea in the Baltic Sea and the Kattegat-Skagerrak. Acronyms: IMR (Institute of Marine Research, Norway), NIVA (Norwegian Institute of Water Research), SAMS (Scottish Association for Marine Science), SMHI (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute), SUHI (Shetland University of the Highlands and Islands), SYKE (Finnish Environment Institute).

The Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) [1,2] is a device for automated unattended phytoplankton analyses. A European IFCB Network was established in May 2021. Users of the instrument in Sweden, Norway, Finland [3] and the United Kingdom met virtually to discuss instrument handling and data processing. The basic premise is to help each other when problems occur and to join forces to develop software for automated identification of organisms. Regular virtual meetings are planned. The long term goal is to set up a European network for unattended automated phytoplankton analyses using platforms such as research vessels, ferrybox systems and fixed stations on islands or moorings. The IFCB can be part of early detection and early warning systems for harmful algae. Other European IFCB users are invited to join the group who will continue cooperation with IFCB users on other continents. The initiative for the European IFCB network came partly from IOC-IPHAB Task Team on the Early Detection, Warning and forecasting or

harmful algal events and the ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics.

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Fig. 2. Examples of images from IFCB. Left: Phytoplankton from the Swedish west coast. Right: Cyanobacteria from Utö Marine Research Station, Northern Baltic Proper.

Fifteenth session of the IOC Inter-governmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB)

In line with Covid-19 restrictions and to limit travel, for the first time since its establishment in 1991 IPHAB was held online (Fig. 1). The fifteenth IPHAB session was held between 23-25 March 2021. The mission of IPHAB is to assess progress, decide on priorities, and identify funding sources and opportunities for implementation of the IOC HAB Programme.

This programme is the only global intergovernmental effort to understand, manage and mitigate the harmful effects of algal blooms. The panel consists

of 8 Task Teams, 5 Regional HAB networks and groups, 2 Expert Working Groups, 1 Steering Committee, and 1 Project group and works closely with the IOC Science and Communication Centre on HAB at the University of Copenhagen Denmark.

This session was the first IPHAB held during the UN Ocean Decade and in opening the session, Dr Vladimir Ryabinin, Executive Secretary of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission and Assistant Director General of UNESCO addressed the delegates

with a reminder of the importance of the work of this panel, the collaborative global work accomplished by our regional groups and topic task teams, and advances since the previous session in particular the completion of the Global HAB Status Report.

Among other topics, the delegates discussed the GlobalHAB Research Programme, Global Assessment of HAB Events, capacity building, a plan for improved research and management of ciguatera, improving HAB forecasting capabilities for more effective mitigation strategies, and a formulation/endorsement of specific objectives for regional activities.

Some major achievements reported, (some still in progress), included:

Fig. 1. Participants attending the XV IPHAB session 23-25 March 2021

- Results from the ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics and ICES-IOC-IMO Working Group on Ballast and other Ship Vectors.
- Updates on the continued publication of the IOC Harmful Algae News.
- Implementation of four training courses.
- Growing development of the regional activities in Western Pacific (IOC/WESTPAC/HAB); the Caribbean (IOC/IOCARIBE/ANCA), South America (IOC/IPHAB/FANSA) and North Africa (IOC/IPHAB/HANA).
- Advances of the PICES HAB-Section and the GlobalHAB publication of “Guidelines for the study of climate change effects on HABs”.
- Contribution to the development of a Technical Guidance Document for the Development of Early Warning Systems for Marine Harmful Algal Bloom Events to be published, as a joint publication of FAO, IOC-UNESCO and IAEA, as a FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper.
- Completion of the Global HAB Status Report and overviews on the IPHAB-IODE Harmful Algae Information System with HAEDAT and OBIS databases as providers of high quality information on HAB events, status and

trends of HAB occurrence and assessment of climate change impacts.

- Advances achieved by the joint interagency strategy for Ciguatera, namely in testing and standards development and availability, and the publication of FAO-WHO Expert Meeting Report on Ciguatera.
- Developments under the joint IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB science programme such as the assessment of economic impacts of HABs in collaboration with NOWPAP, PICES and NOAA;
- Opportunities the UN Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development bring to IPHAB for transformative science solutions for sustainable development of the ocean in relation to HABs and
- Development of activities and partnerships carried out by the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) to promote and foster research and training on HABs.

Commenting on the session, the chairperson of the panel Joe Silke (Ireland) said “IPHAB has continued a broad engagement between the science and management community of our activities, the strengthening of collaborations between IOC HAB groups in particular has led to sharing knowledge, guidance and capacity building; and

further progress including implementation of early warning systems”. He also stated “Further developments including the development of autonomous observing systems and molecular based approaches are bringing new HAB knowledge and the definition of future mitigation strategies”

IPHAB 15 took eight decisions and endorsed two recommendations concerning the work-plan and terms of reference. Work will continue on topics such as the regional task teams, early warning, database developments and global HAB status report, ciguatera strategies, desalination and HABs, monitoring of biotoxins and regulations, algal taxonomy and fish killing microalgae. These decisions were presented for the consideration of the IOC Assembly and were approved at its fiftieth session on June 18th.

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ICES-IOC WGHBD

The ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGHABD) held its annual meeting, online, from 20th to 23rd April 2021 where 40 participants attended. Dave Clarke, Marine Institute is the current chair for the new three year reporting cycle.

During the course of the meeting there were presentations and updates from WG members on the activities of related bodies and groups including IOC UNESCO updates (IPHAB XV UN Decade of Ocean Science (2021-2030), Harmful Algal News, training courses and the International Phytoplankton Inter-comparison exercise) and an update on GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee activities. There was a series of presentations from WG members who are participating in a number of IPHAB

Task Teams which include; and updates on the harmful algal information system (HAIS) and the first Global HAB Status Report.

The meeting also kicked off the new 3 year cycle of Terms of Reference (ToR's) with nine ToR's for the current 2021-2023 cycle. Highlighted ToR's include: a) Investigating the climate-driven changes in the distribution of planktonic and benthic HAB taxa (incl. cyanobacteria); b) Examining fish mortalities and the impact of sub lethal effects and the role of harmful phytoplankton as multi-stress contributors to fish morbidity; c) Molecular methods for the study and monitoring of HAB species and d) Implementation of automated observation systems for harmful algal bloom observations to improve

early detection. Standing ToR's of North Atlantic area countries National Reports for 2020, and also on the updating of the Harmful Algal Events Database were also discussed.

The next WGHABD meeting is scheduled to take place from 5th to 8th April 2022. For more information contact:

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Maria Anna Faust

1930-2021

Dr. Maria Anna Faust (néé Spillenberg), aquatic microbiologist and research botanist emerita from the Smithsonian Institution, passed away on April 24, 2021, at the age of 91 from complications related to a stroke.

Maria Anna Spillenberg was born in Budapest, Hungary on April 21, 1930, with her twin sister Marta, to Anna Maria and George Spillenberg. Her childhood was spent in a small, close knit Hungarian village near Budapest. As a young girl, she endured the onset and duration of World War II. Her father, a medical doctor, was called into the Hungarian military and left his young family behind until after the war.

Maria received her Bachelor of Arts degree in 1951 from the Agricultural University of Budapest where she met Miklos Faust, the love of her life. They wed on July 17, 1954, and welcomed their daughter, Judit, two years later. The onset of the communist political system in Hungary provided many challenges which lead to the abrupt departure of Maria's family to Yugoslavia in 1957. They remained there in a refugee camp for 20 months awaiting asylum to the United Kingdom, Australia or the United States, whichever country would accept their petition first. Upon arrival to the United States, Maria, Miklos, Judit and Maria's parents worked toward a new life making their way from humble beginnings. The Faust and Spillenberg families valued education and felt it was a way of securing their futures. Consequently, Maria earned a master's degree in microbiology at Rutgers University in 1962, followed by a doctoral degree in aquatic microbiology at the University of Maryland at College Park in 1970.

Maria's earliest published work (Faust, 1969*) was on the effect of respiratory inhibitors and membrane-active compounds on bacterial motility followed by comparisons between bacterial and algal utilization of orthophosphate in estuaries. Her research interests lead to a postdoctoral fellowship at the Smithsonian Radiation Biology Laboratory (SRBL) in Rockville, MD in 1971 where Maria worked with Dr. Elizabeth Gantt. Maria accepted a position at the SRBL in 1973 but it was closed a

few years later. Maria was reassigned and continued her work as aquatic microbiologist at the Smithsonian Environmental Research Center (SERC) in Edgewater, MD. There her focus was on a series of prescient water quality studies. These included the relationship between land use practices and fecal bacteria in soils, organic carbon release by phytoplankton, transport of bacteria in temperate marsh sediments, tidal transport of microorganisms in brackish marshes and nutrient fluxes in tributaries of the Chesapeake Bay. Maria's

dedicated work set the stage for subsequent environmentally relevant efforts to inform management decisions. One of her contributions at SERC was a pontoon boat duly named, the *Queen Maria*. This barge is still afloat and functioning in the same capacity it was designed for – a stable work platform for sampling on Muddy Creek and the Rhode River.

In 1983, at a juncture in her career, Maria attended an intensive three-week workshop in Advanced Phytoplankton Taxonomy. This was the third in a series of courses which started in 1976 upon the recommendation of the SCOR Working Group of Phytoplankton Methods that was organized in Drobak, Norway by the Marine Botany Section of the

Plate1: Field photos. A. Smithsonian's Field Station at Carrie Bow Cay (CBC), Belize 2009; B. CBC May 2001; C. Smithsonian's Field Laboratory at Ft. Pierce, FL July 2009; D. CBC May 2004 (front row: Marta Nicholas, Maria Faust, Pat Tester, R.J. Chrost; back row: Sabrina Varnam, Bert Pfeiffer, Steve Kibler, Mark Vandersea); E. Celebrating Maria's birthday at the Smithsonian's Field Laboratory at Ft. Pierce, FL July 2009. (front row Maria, Pat Tester; back row Steve Kibler, Chris Holland, Mark Vandersea); F. Maria at the Smithsonian's Field Station at Carrie Bow Cay (CBC), Belize; G. Maria collecting dinoflagellates at South Water Cay, Belize, May 2002; H. Maria isolating dinoflagellates at CBC May 2004; I. Morning exercise, "Give me 10 more." CBC May 2003 (Sabrina Varnam, Mark Vandersea, Steve Kibler, Wayne Litaker, Maria); J. CBC sunset

University of Oslo. There Maria and her cohorts, many of whom would become leaders in their field, spent long days and some long nights under the tutelage of outstanding instructors, Grethe Hasle (diatoms) with assistance from Eric Syvertsen, Karen Steidinger (dinoflagellates) with assistance from Karl Tangen, Jahn Thronsen (flagellates), and Berit Heimdal (coccolithophores), with lectures from Barrie Dale.

From that time forward dinoflagellate taxonomy and ecology were Maria's major foci and she never looked back. In 1987 she joined the Department of Botany at the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Museum Support Center (NMNH-MSC) in Suitland, MD where she remained until her retirement in 2009.

A series of studies on *Prorocentrum* (cysts, morphology, growth, photosynthesis, descriptions of nine new species) were published from 1985-1993. Much of her material and inspiration was from exploring the mangrove islands of Twin Cays, Belize, near the Smithsonian's Carrie Bow Cay Field Station on the Meso-American Barrier Reef system located fifteen miles offshore from Dangriga. Maria would return there over thirty times in her efforts to understand the taxonomy and ecology of tropical dinoflagellates more thoroughly. Work from 1994-1998 included her overview of benthic, toxic dinoflagellates and a review their life histories, broadening her interest to include *Ostreopsis* species and mixotrophic feeding by benthic dinoflagellates.

Maria's paper on sand-dwelling dinoflagellates in 1995 described a new *Gambierdiscus* species that she named *Gambierdiscus belizeanus*. This was only the second species of what, at that time, was thought to be a monospecific genus. The only other described *Gambierdiscus* was the type species, *G. toxicus*, described in 1979 by Adachi and Fukuyo from the Gambier Islands in French Polynesia [1]. Her discovery would be followed in rapid succession by the description of three other new species found in the Pacific by Mireille Chinain in collaboration with Serge Pauillac of the Institut Louis Malardé, Tahiti [2]. One of these species, *G. polynesiensis*, would turn out to be the most toxic *Gambierdiscus* known to date. Maria's exquisite electron micrographs and

Plate 2: Professional. A. Maria Spillenberg 1953; B. Participants of the SCOR Working Group on Phytoplankton Methods organized in Drobak, Norway by the Marine Botany Section of the University of Oslo IOC Phytoplankton Course, 1983. Maria is in the front row, sixth from the right; C. Graduation from Rutgers University 1962; D. Phycological Society of America. Award of Excellence, Williamsburg, VA August 2004 (Wayne Litaker and Maria). E. Maria receiving PSA's Award of Excellence, Williamsburg, VA August. F. Smithsonian's Marine Science Symposium, Washington, DC 2007 (Maria and Wayne Litaker); G. Maria in New Caledonia 2008; H. Poster Session, SI's Marine Science Symposium 2007; I. Maria's office at the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Museum Support Center in Suitland, MD, 2005 (Maria and Pat Tester); J. Maria in her lab at the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Museum Support Center in Suitland, MD, 2005

her exacting organizational and record keeping skills in this study would prove most valuable a few years later.

The SEM stub containing preserved material for the GTT-91 isolate of *G. toxicus* from the 1999 study was deposited in the Type Collection of Dinoflagellates at the National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution. In 2009, when no live *G. toxicus* cells could be found, this SEM stub was used as the source for the redescription of the species and designation of an epitype [3]. This monograph described four new *Gambierdiscus* species and provided line drawings, high resolution light micrographs and SEMs of all extant *Gambier-*

discus species as well as sequence data that were deposited in GenBank. This comprehensive publication was subsequently selected for the Tyge Christensen Award for the best paper published in the International Phycological Society's journal *Phycologia* in 2009.

In her 40 year career, Maria published over 120 research papers. A notable publication, *Identifying Harmful Marine Dinoflagellates*, [4], is a taxonomic identification and reference guide of 48 harmful marine dinoflagellate species with descriptions of plate and thecal morphology and excellent scanning

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Gertrud Cronberg

1937-2021

Phycologist Gertrud Cronberg has completed her odyssey.

A pioneer in the study of cyanobacteria and chrysophytes, limnologist professor emerita Gertrud Cronberg has left us. She worked at Lund University for more than 40 years. Gertrud was born in Malmö in 1937. Her interest in small organisms in water was sparked when she read H C Andersen's fairy tale "The Water Drop" as a child. This story describes the marvelous life in a drop of water from a pond and she acquired her own microscope from an early age.

Her father, Hans Hellsten, was head of the infection clinic at Malmö General Hospital, and had the official task of taking water samples from the pond Stora Pildammen, the drinking water source of Malmö. Gertrud often accompanied her father to the pond, and she gained the insight that a drop of water could also contain organisms that caused life-threatening diseases. The relationship between aquatic microbes and diseases, an interest that originated from an early age, became a theme in her research activities throughout her life.

The Hellsten family spent their annual summer holidays in the Höör region of Sweden where they used to swim in Lake Ringsjön. Fifty years later, in a scientific paper on Lake Ringsjön, she described how the lake water in the 1940s was green from cyanobacteria and that she and her siblings got rashes. As a teenager she met the love of her life, medical student Stig Cronberg. After their marriage in 1960 they became the parents of seven children over the course of ten years.

In the late 1960s, Gertrud studied with the legendary phycologist Pierre Bourrelly in Paris. Bourrelly encouraged her to start studying chrysophytes since Sweden is a paradise of chrysophytes. Gertrud heeded his call. She became one of the first to use electron microscopy in Lund and produced thousands of unique images. Chrysophytes form species-specific resting cells that are hidden in the lakes' sediments. Gertrud became a pioneer in using these resting cells to map the historical and

environmental changes in lakes as well as creating a systematic order among cysts from chrysophytes.

Along with the scientific importance, Gertrud's SEM photos with chrysophytes are amazing works of art from nature. Through this photographic art, Gertrud was invited to Oxford where she lectured on art in science.

In 1968, she began her doctoral studies which led to a dissertation and PhD in 1980. Her dissertation "Phytoplankton Changes in Lake Trummen Induced by Restoration" is one of the classic works describing the control of limnic ecosystems. In Lake Trummen, she and her colleagues performed pioneering experiments where the effects of fish on water quality were studied. They were the first to demonstrate that cyanobacterial mass development can be triggered by the addition of benthivorous fish. The results of these experiments inspired lake managers worldwide to reduce cyanobacteria in lakes by reducing benthivorous fish.

During several decades, Gertrud monitored the phytoplankton in hundreds of Swedish lakes. She focused on selected lakes with cyanobacteria blooms such as Lakes Ringsjön and

Finjasjön. In the 1990s, the water quality of these two lakes were improved by the reduction of benthivorous fish. This management action was based on results from the experiments in Lake Trummen.

The presence of *Gonyostomum semen*, a nuisance alga belonging to Raphidophyceae, increased in a large number of Swedish lakes at the end of the last century. *Gonyostomum semen* is problematic because it produces a mucus that can irritate swimmers and clog the gills of fish and bottom-dwelling animals as well as water filters. Gertrud found this alga particularly interesting. In 2005, after decades of research, she revealed the complicated life cycle of *Gonyostomum semen*.

Gertrud's research activities attracted international attention and she conducted extensive research in waters at various latitudes. In Brazil, she participated in a WHO project focusing on Lago Paranoa, near Brasilia. Lago Paranoa was affected by heavy blooms of the cyanobacterium *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii*. Using experiments, Gertrud succeeded in showing how the supply of nutrients triggered the development of cyanobacteria. Through this

research, and her teaching and supervision of technicians, Gertrud received the honorary title, "Mother of Limnology in Brazil".

In the early 1980s, she organized annual UNESCO-sponsored courses on tropical water resources for lake managers. This initiated a project on Lake Kariba, an impounded reservoir that was created on the Zambezi River. Gertrud built up a research station at the Zimbabwean lake side which has been appreciated by a large number of students and scientists.

West of Lake Kariba, the Okavango River forms the world's largest inland delta in the Kalahari desert. The hydrobiology of the delta has been explored under Gertrud's leadership. The algal flora of the Negril and Black River Morasses, Jamaica, the Namn-Guom Reservoir, Laos, and the lakes around Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam also became parts of her field research.

Alone, or together with colleagues, Gertrud has discovered 91 species and varieties of algae and published approximately 100 scientific papers. Three algal species have been named after her;

the chrysophytes *Synura cronbergiae* P.A.Siver and *Mallomonas cronbergiae* Piatek, the cyanobacterium *Chroococcus cronbergiae* Komárek & E.Novelo and the cyanobacterial genus *Cronbergia* J. Komárek, E.Zapomelová & F.Hindák, with four species.

During her expeditions around large parts of the world, Gertrud collected thousands of algal samples that were carefully studied and photographed. Gertrud was the co-author of a handbook on cyanobacteria, published by IOC-UNESCO and ISSHA in 2006, in which many of her beautiful images of cyanobacteria were presented. Her wide-ranging knowledge on harmful algae made her an important investigator when solving the cause of waterborne outbreaks.

She lived a life in wonder and curiosity with the constant passion for the diversity of life in a drop of water. Her work was characterised by professionalism, integrity and courage. Gertrud never hesitated to raise her voice against bullying or abuse of power.

Gertrud generously shared her knowledge with students and col-

leagues from all over the world. She was always keen to build up local skills in the countries she visited and therefore supervised a large number of master's and doctoral students from Asia, Europe and Africa. She opened her and Stig's home to them with warmth and her generous hospitality.

Gertrud is mourned by her husband Stig, seven children and families, twelve grandchildren, relatives and friends from all over the world.

We are many who will sincerely miss Gertrud and who feel a genuine and profound gratitude for what she has meant to us and to numerous others.

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electron and light micrographs. This contribution from the US National Herbarium has been widely distributed to and valued by students and researchers worldwide. It assisted in Maria's love of teaching. She freely shared her expertise and experiences with others by inviting them to visit her laboratory, sharing the research facilities at Carrie Bow Cay, Belize or spending time with them at the poster sessions at meetings. She was a strong supporter of the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae and a member of the American Phycological Society, attending their meetings and contributing regularly. In 2004, Maria was honored by the Award

of Excellence from the Phycological Society of America. Maria will be remembered for many things including her technically exquisite and artistic microscopy (SEM). But most of all she will be remembered for her old-world graciousness, her kindness, her wisdom and eagerness to share her knowledge and passion for dinoflagellates.

*See a full list of Dr. Faust's publications at <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=VWu61XsAAAAJ&hl=en>

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ISSHA's Corner

The **19th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA 2021)** will be held for the first time from 10th - 15th of October using an on-line format from La Paz, B.C.S., Mexico. We have received a total of 403 contributions divided between 9 plenary speakers, 244 oral presentations, 40 speed talks and 110 posters from 47 countries. Over 700 participants have registered for the conference!

The plenary talks will be given by outstanding researchers in different fields of harmful algae: Beatriz Reguera, Marie Yasmine Dechraoui, Michelle Burford, Christopher Whithead, Ernesto García Mendoza, Uwe John, Iwataki Mitsunori, Alexandra Worden and Jorge Mardones.

Several generous sponsors covered the registration fees of 77 participants from 13 countries.

- We will also have six special sessions which will be led different specialists:

ICHA

19th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HARMFUL ALGAE

MEXICO 2021

LA PAZ
baja california sur

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www.icha2021.com

- The Young Investigator Networking Session
- HAB Early Warning Systems Session
- Impacts of HABs on fish farms: Ad-

ressing industry and global insurance needs

- Control of Cyanobacterial Blooms
- NHABON-NE (National HAB Observing Network in the Northeast USA), a prototype node for a national HAB sensor network in the United States
- The presentation of a new book, 'WHO guidance on cyanotoxins' by Ingrid Chorus

During the conference, awards will be given to outstanding ISSHA members for their relevant and long-standing contribution in the study of harmful algae, to young scientists that have made a -break through- contribution in the field, as well as for the best oral and poster student presentation.

For more details on this conference visit our website: <http://www.icha2021.com/Secciones/inicio>

Elections for International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) Officers and Council members

One of the benefits of the membership of the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) is the ability to vote for new Council members and Officers of the Society. Please take a moment to read the [candidate bios](#) and to vote using this link

[here](#) by midnight La Paz, Mexico time on October 10, 2021. You will be required to login to the [ISSHA website](#) with your username and password. A password reset option is also provided.

The winners will be announced at the General Assembly meeting during

the [ICHA2021 conference](#) on Monday, October 11, 2021. I look forward to "seeing" you at the Conference. Please vote!

Most sincerely,
Vera Trainer (ISSHA President)

Eds-in-chief

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

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